

First-year undergraduate student proficiency in Educational Digital Foundations (EDFs): An analysis by gender, geographic origin and prior computer studies experience

Research questionnaire - Key

The sample consisted of first-year undergraduate students who reported their proficiency in EDFs on a Likert scale from 1 ("Very Poor") to 5 ("Very Good"). Therefore, the maximum score that was achieved per item was 5 and the minimum was 1.

VARIABLES	QUESTION IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE	MEASURE
Gender1	Male [] Female []	Nominal
Environment2	Characterise the environment of your residence	Nominal
Environment3	Have you taken a Computer Studies course at secondary school?	Nominal
Proficient4	How do you regard your typing Skills Microsoft word	Ordinal
Proficient5	How do you regard proofreading and Editing Skills in Microsoft word	Ordinal
Proficient6	How do you regard your data input accuracy in Excel	Ordinal
Proficient7	How do you regard data analysis in Excel	Ordinal
Proficient8	How do you regard your creation of visually appealing slides in PowerPoint	Ordinal
Proficient9	How do you regard your skills in using PowerPoint	Ordinal
Proficient10	How do you regard your assignment Presentation and Organization in Microsoft word	Ordinal
Proficient11	How do you regard your making of useful animations and transitions in your presentations	Ordinal
Proficient12	How do you regard your design and formatting of text	Ordinal
Proficient13	How do you regard your use of Google and other search engines.	Ordinal
Proficient14	How do you regard your proficient in searching for specific keywords using google or other search engines.	Ordinal
Proficient15	How do you regard your familiarity with various search engines such as Google.	Ordinal
Proficient16	How do you regard your skills in locating study materials online.	Ordinal
Proficient17	How do you regard your confidence in using YouTube as a resource for study	Ordinal
Proficient18	How do you regard your effectiveness in searching for solutions to my assignments on the internet	Ordinal